

STUDY OF THE PROBLEM OF INTELLECTUAL EMOTIONS IN STUDENTS BY WORLD PSYCHOLOGISTS

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Abstract. *In this article, intellectual feelings are studied by psychologists for the first time, intellectual feelings express the relationship of success and failure in the process of knowledge, it is formed in the cognitive attitude of a person to the world and is directly related to a better understanding of the world, and the process of learning is also a result of it. Also, the views of many scientists about intellectual emotions and their opinions about its types have been studied.*

Keywords: *feeling, intellectual feelings, cognitive activity, doubt, feeling of surprise, feeling of surprise, feeling of confidence.*

Intellectual feelings express and reflect the relationship of success and failure in the process of cognition. Deep connections between mental and emotional processes that develop together have been identified in psychology. In the process of learning, a person always puts forward hypotheses, rejects or confirms them, and looks for the most correct ways to solve a problem. The search for truth can be accompanied by a sense of doubt. Two or more conflicting ideas exist in the subject's mind about possible ways to solve the problem. Whether or not what a person believes and what he learns is a complex cognitive process, and the place of intellectual feeling is incomparable in it.

Intellectual feelings are a person's cognitive attitude to the world, and the process of acquiring knowledge is also its result. Intellectual feelings include curiosity, doubt, surprise. The pinnacle of intellectual feelings is the generalized feeling of love for truth, which becomes a great driving force contributing to the deep penetration into the mysteries of existence.

Feelings are created by the events and imaginations we perceive, imagine and think, as well as by our actions. Not only because things are being perceived, imagined and thought, but because these things are connected to a certain extent with our needs and interests, they create different feelings in us, if the things we imagine and think about are not related to our needs and interests, we do not have significant emotions. Such things are often overlooked [1]. An emotion is a need-related phenomenon, and an emotion arises when a need or benefit is fulfilled or not increased.

From this it can be known that the feelings related to cognitive activity are intellectual feelings and play the main role in the regulation of intellectual activity. Examples of these feelings are interest, satisfaction, love of truth, doubt, surprise, and others. Intellectual feelings make it possible to overcome difficulties and support the desire to search for truth. That is why the work done by some scientists is very surprising. The reason is that the intellectual senses of scientists are very well developed, they study everything with interest and analyze it deeply. When they start a task, they focus on it.

Intellectual feelings mean specific experiences that arise in the process of mental activity in a person. The term "intellectual feeling" appeared in the school of I. Herbert in the first half of the 19th century. (Herbart, 1834). However, representatives of this school considered these

feelings either as characteristics of feelings or as a manifestation of the dynamics of ideas. Basically, they believed that intellectual feeling in their understanding is nothing more than a conscious assessment of cognitive processes and the relationships between them. Therefore, as intellectual feelings, they singled out the search for novelty, confrontation, emotional change, surprise. In the works of R. Descartes (1950) and B. Spinoza (1957), they added surprise, certainty and doubt to intellectual feelings. A. Behn (1906) referred to intellectual feelings as wonder, surprise, novelty, truth and falsehood, as well as internal consistency and inconsistency. K. D. Ushinsky (1950) considered the sense of "comparison" or "comparison" of similarity and difference to be the leading mental sense. He also called intellectual feelings expectation, surprise, lie, irreconcilable contradiction, mental strain, mental success or failure, surprise, doubt, confidence T. Ribault (1898), E. Titchener (1898), U. James (1922) wrote about intellectual feelings in his work[9]. Moreover, if the first of these authors speaks of wonder, passion, which can be associated with affective reactions, then the second two are perceived as intellectual feelings by cognitive processes: or judgments resulting from logical operations, as in E. Titchener such as - agreement, conflict, convenience or difficulty, truth or falsehood, certainty or uncertainty, or non-figurative elements of thought, as in W. James - analogy, implication, coincidence, relations between objects of thought, etc. As we can see, in these cases we are not talking about the experiences of the subject.

Therefore, since the listed intellectual phenomena (cognitive processes) were applied by K. D. Ushinsky, E. Titchener, W. James and others to intellectual feelings only without distinguishing the term "feeling", in fact, the processes of conscious human thought and until now wonder, guessing, confidence, doubt are called intellectual feelings (I. A. Vasiliev). This author commented on their genetic connection with special functional - mental activity. "They appear not only in the process of mental activity," writes Vasiliev, "but are directed at it, evaluate its success and failure in terms of the motives of mental activity, and based on this assessment, they actively influence the course of the thinking process in order to ultimately satisfy the cognitive needs of the subject." they show a secret."

Despite belonging to such broad functional "obligations", in relation to intellectual feelings, it remains completely unclear what distinguishes them from the feelings associated with the result of mental activity (joy, satisfaction, satisfaction, or vice versa, disappointment, restlessness, anger).

The peculiarity of the feelings classified as intellectual is their division into valence (opposite) color (pleasant and unpleasant), as shown by the mirror. K. Izard (2000) and R. Plutchik (Plutchik, 1980). As a result, he said that the contrast appears and brings out intellectual feelings such as surprise, interest, and doubt.

The highest human senses are moral, aesthetic and intellectual senses. Intellectual sensibilities arise in the process of education and are manifested in scientific works, as well as in various creative activities such as art, science and technology. These aspects are strong in people who find their place in the field of science and art.

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